

Lattice Boltzmann Simulation of the carbonization of wood particle

Authors : Ahmed Mahmoudi, Imen Mejri, Mohamed A. Abbassi, Ahmed Omri

Abstract : A numerical study based on the lattice Boltzmann method (LBM) is proposed to solve one, two and three dimensional heat and mass transfer for isothermal carbonization of thick wood particles. To check the validity of the proposed model, computational results have been compared with the published data and a good agreement is obtained. Then, the model is used to study the effect of reactor temperature and thermal boundary conditions, on the evolution of the local temperature and the mass distributions of the wood particle during carbonization.

Keywords : lattice Boltzmann method, pyrolysis conduction, carbonization, Heat and mass transfer

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